

УДК 372.881.111

**"AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AND PROJECT WORK IN LANGUAGE LEARNING:
BENEFITS, CHALLENGES, AND APPLICATIONS"**

KALIEVA AKERKE ASKHATOVNA

Student of ALT University

Scientific supervisor - **SHAIZHANOVA MERUYERT MARATOVNA**

Almaty, Kazakhstan

Annotation. *This paper explores the role of authentic materials and project work in foreign language education. Drawing on Alejandro G. Martinez's (2002) work, it outlines the definition of authentic materials, their sources, and the key advantages and disadvantages of using them in the classroom. It emphasizes that authentic resources, while sometimes challenging due to cultural and linguistic barriers, can enrich language instruction by exposing learners to real-world contexts and diverse language forms. The paper also discusses alternative views, particularly Claire Kramsch's perspective on authenticity as a construct shaped by interaction between text and learner. In the second part, the paper focuses on project-based learning, referencing Tom Hutchinson and others. It highlights the motivational, communicative, and developmental benefits of projects, especially in mixed-ability and inclusive classrooms. The integration of real-life tasks with creative, student-centered learning is presented as a powerful method for enhancing both language proficiency and personal growth.*

Keywords: *authentic materials, language learning, communicative competence, project work, motivation, mixed-ability classes, learner independence, cultural competence, real-life tasks, cross-curricular learning.*

Introduction. In recent years, language education has increasingly emphasized communicative competence and real-world language use over rote memorization and artificial textbook exercises. As a result, the integration of authentic materials—resources created for native speakers and not originally intended for instructional use—has gained significant attention. These materials, ranging from newspapers and websites to menus and song lyrics, offer learners exposure to natural language and diverse cultural contexts, making the learning process more meaningful and engaging.

At the same time, project-based learning has emerged as an effective method for promoting active student participation, creativity, and learner autonomy. Projects encourage students to use the target language in practical, personalized ways that reflect their interests and real-life experiences. Together, authentic materials and project work support a communicative and student-centered approach to language teaching.

This paper examines the benefits, challenges, and practical applications of authentic materials and project work in language learning. It draws on key educational theorists such as Alejandro G. Martinez, Claire Kramsch, and Tom Hutchinson to explore how these methods can be adapted for learners of different proficiency levels and integrated into modern language classrooms to enhance both linguistic skills and personal development.

An Overview (2002) by Alejandro G. Martinez deals with the term authentic materials itself and with advantages and disadvantages of their use as well as possible sources of them. Authentic materials: “Sometimes called “authentic” or “contextualized”, real-life materials are those that a student encounters in everyday life but that weren’t created for educational purposes. They include newspapers, magazines, and Web sites, as well as driver’s manuals, utility bills, pill bottles, and clothing labels.”

Martinez mentions Widdowson’s differentiation between authentic and genuine materials. Authentic materials are materials created for native speaker of the language and use in a class in its

original form and design. In other words, they are not changed in any way. Whereas genuine materials are authentic materials adapted for a class, e. g. jumbled paragraphs, cut out headlines etc.

Martinez listed following pluses and minuses:

Advantages:

- There is factual acquisition from most of them;
- Textbooks do not include inaccurate language;
- Authentic materials may be inspirational for some pupils;
- One piece of text may be used for various activities and tasks;
- There is a wide choice of styles, genres and formality in authentic texts;
- They can motivate pupils to read for pleasure.

Disadvantages:

- Authentic texts may be difficult to understand because of a culture gap;
- The vocabulary may be not exactly what the students need;
- They are rather difficult for beginners;
- Preparation of the texts and activities is often demanding and time consuming;
- There are many various accents and dialects in listening;
- The materials become outdated quickly (news).

Sources of authentic materials

Newspapers, menus, magazines, the Internet, TV programs, movies, CDs, songs, brochures, comics, literature (novels, poems and short stories), catalogues, leaflets, tickets, postcards, bills, receipts, wrappings, recipes, business cards, labels, stamps, etc.

Where to get authentic materials?

- the Internet;
- library

There is usually an English department in every city or university library. There can be found not only books, but also magazines and music.

- a foreign country.

Main part. When visiting an English speaking country, one should think about the great opportunity to get authentic materials. On British Council web pages, there are described some aspects of using authentic materials. One of them is difficultness of such materials. There is said that they are difficult, but that is the point. Moreover, the trick is to set the task according to the level of the students, not to choose the material according to the students' level.

However, for lower levels are suitable leaflets, menus, timetables, video and audio advertisements, short reports, short news. The tasks should be rather simple and vocabulary should be introduced in advance. Excessive materials for intermediate levels can be longer articles and news or reports, whole TV programmes. The vocabulary should be pre-taught, too. With advanced students, any authentic material can be used. Pre-teaching is not necessary, but it is good to have some explanations and definitions prepared.

Claire Kramsch had a different view on authentic materials. In her book *Context and Culture in Language Teaching* (1996), she devoted one chapter to authentic texts and contexts. She agrees with Widdowson's definition: "It is probably better to consider authenticity not as a quality residing in instances of language but as a quality which is bestowed upon them, created by the response of the receiver. Authenticity in this view is a function of the interaction between the reader/hearer and the text which incorporates the intentions of the writer/speaker... Authenticity has to do with appropriate response."

As an example, she mentions a German menu, which would not be authentic text if it was used in an English lesson to practice reading prices or learning adjective endings. It would be an authentic piece of text if it was used as a German menu.

Next she says that cultural competence does not include the obligation to behave according to conventions of given speech community and that we should not want our student to behave like

somebody else or plagiarize behavioural patterns. Behaving like someone else is not a guarantee that the community that speaks the language will accept the person.

In *Introduction to Project Work* (1992) by Tom Hutchinson, specifics of project working are described. A project is a result of hard work, because the authors have to find information for their project, get pictures or draw some, make a draft containing their ideas, then put everything together and complete the text, the result of which is a presentation.

“A project is an extended piece of work on a particular topic where the content and the presentation are determined principally by the learners.”

The teacher can provide the topic, but the authors decide themselves what exactly are they going to write and how will they present it. Because a project is a creative task, it is also personal. The reason for doing project work are based on the fact that there is a strong communicative aspect, which enables the students to use the language in something real, not in an artificial exercise. Principal elements of communicative approach are a concern for motivation, a concern for relevance and a concern for educational values. Motivation is a crucial key for successful learning. Project work is especially useful for developing positive motivation.

As mentioned above, projects are personal. The students write about their lives, their families, their cities or their researches into topics that interest them. Because of such personal approach, both sense of the project and its presentation are important for students. Projects are not simulations. They are real.

Projects are also very operative. It is actually a play. The learners have to collect information, draw pictures, maps or charts, cut out pictures, carry out interviews and surveys and make recordings.

Diane Phillips, Sarah Burwood and Helen Dunfold say in their publication *Projects with Young Learners* (2003) that projects develop children’s whole personality:

- intellectual skills (describing, drawing, imagination, reading, planning)
- physical / motor skills (colouring, painting, folding, cutting etc.)
- social skills (sharing, cooperation, making decisions, appreciating individual contributions)
- learner independence (making responsible choices, getting information, evaluating results).

According to Hutchinson, project work enables all students to produce a worthwhile product. Therefore it is highly suitable for mixed ability classes and for students with special educational needs. The brighter students can work faster while at the same time, the slower students can work in their own pace and produce something they can be proud of. They can use more visual aid to compensate their language imperfection.

The advantages of projects according to Phillips, Burwood and Dunfold are:

- The project focus is on all aspects of children’s life, not only on their linguistic competences. Therefore they can easily relate what they know from their lives to concrete problems.
- Projects encourage students to be responsible for their work and their learning.
- Projects allow students with different competences cooperate when working out the project. It is a kind of solution for mixed – ability classes.
- Personal involvement is high, which support students’ motivation for further learning.

Hutchinson says that projects are good for integration of foreign languages into learner’s communicative competence. “It encourages the use of a wide range of communicative skills, enables learners to exploit other spheres of knowledge, and provides opportunities for them to write about things that are important in their own lives.” The language used in projects is more relevant to students’ needs. They can rehearse use of language, which would be the most useful for them in real life.

There is a big culture part in project work. The learner can not only mention their own culture, but also explore into foreign cultures and compare them with each other.

Project work supports independent work, cooperation, imagination and self-discipline. These are some of the basic aims in the most curricula. Recently, the requirement of cross-curricular learning has been raised and anchored in Czech Framework Educational Programme. Project work obviously encourages using knowledge gained in other subjects such as Geography, History, civics etc.

There are also some disadvantages in project working.

Firstly, there may be more noise in the classroom when the students are working out their projects. However, Hutchinson claims that there is not really a problem of noise, but a problem of control. The teacher has to be able to manage the class during such an alternative way of work as well as during common teaching. There will always be some noise, because the students need to discuss some thing with their classmates and need to borrow some tools or books. But it is a natural noise, which is comparable with noise made during common teaching: teacher's strong voice or whole class repeating after the teacher can be even noisier.

Secondly, time management is definitely a thing to consider. If a project is a group work, most of it must be done at school. But students can work outside the class, too. They can have some partial or individual tasks to work out.

Lastly, the teacher has to decide whether he prefers the students to speak only English all the time or whether they can use their mother tongue, too. Hutchinson says that it does not matter when they use mother tongue. We should rather consider its merits than to see it as a problem. The product will be English anyway, so we can allow the learners to use their mother tongue during working it out.

For teachers, project work has a wide use. It is a flexible methodology, which can be applied on every level except of complete beginners. It is suitable for all ages.

The teacher should choose the topic according to the age of his students, their interests, level of English, available sources and the amount of time which can be devoted to the project.

Susan Stempleski and Barry Tomalin suggest in their book *Video in Action*, (1990) some good reasons why to use video in teaching and some important and useful points to concentrate on.

First of all, it is a big motivation. Students become interested faster when experiencing the language in a lively and amusing way, i. e. through pictures, in this case moving pictures (films, documents, broadcasting etc.). In combination with sounds, video interprets the language in a comprehensive and realistic way.

Secondly, video often makes students more communicative in target language.

Thirdly, non-verbal aspects of communication are presented, too. Robert Merabian, the American psychologist, said that 80 percent of human communication is non-verbal. Our expressions, gestures, posture and clothing is equal to what we say. We can see those aspects in motion on a video. Moreover, the teacher can freeze any moment he wants to and discuss it with the students.

Finally, cross-cultural comparison is an indivisible feature of authentic materials. Observing differences in culture is essential for understanding other nations. Awareness of cultural background is important in learning a language. Therefore it is essential to highlight cultural habits, too.

Stempleski and Tomalin say that video can be used at any level. It can be used as a supplementary material time to time, e. g. one a week, or it can be a part of every lesson if the course is based on it. Because video is a highly motivating device, it is useful for beginners and elementary levels as the good motivation at the beginning is crucial. Usage of video depends, of course, on sources, technical equipment and amount of time, which can be devoted to it.

The students should be actively involved when watching. They should know in advance what are they going to watch before they get some tasks connected with watching. Active watching is especially important in watching recipes.

Revision of vocabulary – students' vocabulary can be exercised and reviewed. Building vocabulary – new vocabulary or lexical units can be introduced and acquired from a certain sequence.

Revision of grammar – grammar already known to students can be toughened up. Grammar presentation – certain grammatical structures are presented.

According to Tomalin and Stempleski, it is important to prepare the lesson plan and the material thoroughly. It might be time-consuming, but once it is done, it can be used again next year in other class and other teachers can use it, too.

When selecting a sequence, the teacher should choose a suitable part, which the students will be interested in. They usually do not consider a video to be an educational material. It is rather

entertainment for them. If it were a boring sequence for them, they would not be willing to learn through it. The length should be adequate to the length of the lesson, to the level of the students and their age. The shortest sequence may be about thirty seconds long.

It should be possible to use the sequence for more than one activity. Otherwise it may be waste of time. The teacher has to consider his pupils' skills carefully. The level of language in the sequence should be neither too low nor too high for them. However, it is not a crucial parameter when choosing a sequence. The teacher can still provide the script and the video will provide the context, which is a basic clue to understand it.

Next he should consider whether there are the relevant language items that he intends to present to the students. If his intention is a revision of vocabulary, it is necessary the sequence to contain it.

The teacher is recommended by the authors to use scripts with the video itself as well. He should use it not only in the lesson, but also during the preparation, because it will show him what language is used. The video itself will show behaviour and context. The video and the script complement each other.

Once the teacher has chosen a sequence, he may need to prepare some worksheets. He may need and overhead projector presentation, extra activities, transcripts of dialogues, commentaries etc.

Conclusion. During my work, I have found out that authentic materials play an important role in teaching a second language. They enrich the traditional lessons and are interesting for students, too. However, the pupils are not used to learning from alternative sources. They do not have much responsibility for their learning. In my opinion, they should be taught independence since early age. It is demanding to prepare a lesson with use of authentic materials and it is also not easy to get the materials, too. It may be one of the reasons why they are not used much. I very appreciate the possibility to try to implement authentic materials into teaching. In future, I will be aware of some difficulties, which may unexpectedly appear. I will not condemn authentic materials at all. I still consider them to be very useful and enriching. I will keep collecting them and finding ways of using them.

The work deals with use of authentic materials, such as books, video, music etc. in teaching English language. It refers to specialized sources and gives reasons for authentic materials usage. Particular attention is drawn to multicultural background. Another important feature which the work deals with is practical use of authentic materials in real environment of a primary school. The work describes the process and elaborates the results.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Dickinson, Leslie. *Self-instruction in Language Learning*. Cambridge University Press, 2000, pp. 23–45.
2. Gill, Simon, and Michaela Čaňková. *Intercultural Activities*. Oxford University Press, 2002, pp. 10–27.
3. Hutchinson, Tom. *Introduction to Project Work*. Oxford University Press, 2000, pp. 5–19.
4. Jones, Ken. *Simulations in Teaching*. Cambridge University Press, 1990, pp. 30–52.
5. Kramsch, Claire. *Context and Culture in Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press, 2000, pp. 60–78.
6. Lewis, Gordon. *The Internet and Young Learners*. Oxford University Press, 2004, pp. 15–33.
7. Phillips, Diane, Sarah Burwood, and Helen Dunford. *Projects with Young Learners*. Oxford University Press, 2003, pp. 40–58.
8. Stempleski, Susan, and Barry Tomalin. *Video in Action*. Cambridge University Press, 2000, pp. 12–26.
9. Teeler, Dede, and Peta Gray. *How to Use the Internet in ELT*. Pearson Education Limited, 2000, pp. 50–70.
10. Tomalin, Barry, and Susan Stempleski. *Cultural Awareness*. Oxford University Press, 2000, pp. 33–47.